

Influence of GA3 (Gibberellic Acid) and Salinity on Seeds Germination Indices and Seedling Characteristics of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

Fatima Abdallah Mohammed Ahmed¹; Doha ALi AL-Smmani Mohamed²; Badr ELdin Abdelgadir Mohammed Ahmed^{3*}

¹Assistant Professor; ²Assistant Professor; ³Associated Professor

¹Education Faculty, Department of Chemistry and Biology; University of Gadarif, Sudan

²Corporation of Agricultural Research, Khartoum, Sudan

³Crop Sciences Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Kassala University, Sudan

Corresponding Author:- Badr ELdin Abdelgadir Mohammed Ahmed^{3*}

Abstract:- A Petri dishes laboratory experiment of RCBD with three replicates was conducted during 2023/2024 winter season at Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kassala, New Halfa, Sudan. to investigate the effect of (GA3) on seed germination and seedling of wheat plant under salinity levels. GA3 treatments are four rates of GA3 G₀, G₁₀₀, G₁₅₀ and G₂₀₀ corresponding to (0,100,150 and 200 p.p.m) and three levels of salinity S₀, S₅₀ and S₁₀₀ corresponding to (0, 50 and 100 milimose) prepared from equal equivalents of NaCl. The results revealed that, both of salinity and GA3 treatments affected final germination percentage (FGP%), mean germination time (MGT), Speed of Daily germination (DGS) and index of seedling vigor (SVI). Increasing GA3 level up to 150 p.p.m increased FGP,DGS,MGT and SVI. On contrast, increasing salt concentration resulting up to 100 milimoses in decreased of FGP,DGS and SVI. In conclusion, it was concluded that applied of GA3 at recommended levels lessened the harmful of salinity on germination indices and growth of seedling in wheat seeds.

Keywords:- Wheat; Gabralline GA3; Salinity, Germination Indices and Seedling Vigor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) belonged to Graminae family [1]. It is widely adapted plant grown in different environments (humid and dry [2]. It is the most important cereal crop grown all over the world. Wheat is low cost of production crop which adapted to various climates[3]. Many investigators [4-6] studied the hormones effect on germination of seed, they reported that, during the embryo development, endogenous plant hormones Gibberellins (GA3) increase in the embryo while the developing embryo is heterotrophic (dependant on the mother tissue for support). High levels of GA3 increased all indices of germination and characters growth of seedlings on contrast increasing levels of salinity decreased these characters in maize [7]. Recently [8] reported significant differences in germination indices due to application of gibberellic acid[8]. However, increasing GA3concentration to high salinity levels treatment decreased

germination days [9]. About 7% of land area in the world is affected by salinity and wheat growth and yield were affected by salinity [10-12]. Salinity, in general, has inhibitory Also, other researchers reported the adverse effects of salinity on seed germination [13-15]. Application of GA3 reduced the adverse effect of [16-17]. Different strategies have been employed to enhanced germination of seed and growth of seedling under saline conditions. Few studies, In Sudan, have been conducted to study effects of growth hormones compared to control on seeds germination particularly under saline water. Hence these factors interrelate providing an important insight to the study of their interaction on seeds germination and seedling growth. So, the this study was conducted to determine if salinity stress can be modified by GA3 application through investigating the interactive effects of salt stress and GA3 on germination of seeds and seedlings growth of wheat.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A Petri dishes laboratory experiment of RCBD with three replicates was conducted during 2023/2024 winter season at Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kassala, New Halfa, Sudan. to investigate the effect of (GA3) on seed germination and seedling of wheat plant under salinity levels. GA3 treatments are four rates of GA3 G₀, G₁₀₀, G₁₅₀ and G₂₀₀ corresponding to (0,100,150 and 200 p.p.m) and three levels of salinity S₀, S₅₀ and S₁₀₀ corresponding to (0, 50 and 100 mM) prepared from equal equivalents of NaCl.

➤ Germination Test

3% sodium hypochlorite was used for sterilizing seeds for 3 minutes then washed with distilled water. In a glass petri dish of 9 cm diameter with filter paper, 10 seeds were placed and 16 ml salinity solution of desired treatment was added. Germination of Seed was recorded daily at a certain time. After the 12th day, radicle and plumule lengths were measured.

➤ The Following Germination Traits were Measured:

Final Germination percentage (FGP) [%] using the formula described by [18], Mean germination time (MGT) [Days] using the formula described by[19],

Germination energy (GE) [%] and Daily germination speed (DGS): using the formulas described by [20]. Also, Seedling vigor index (SVI) Calculated as follows.

$SVI = (\text{Radicle length} + \text{plumule length}) \times FEP\%$ as described by [20].

➤ Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed according to (ANOVA) for RCBD using statistical analysis package (Statistix 10). Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) used for mean comparisons at 5% probability level.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Treatments of both GA3 and salinity were showed significant effects on all studied traits but their interaction was significant only on DGS (Table 1). In this regard, Increasing GA3 level up to 150 p.p.m resulted in increased of FGP, DGS, MGT and SVI as compared to its relative treatments (figures 1,2,3,4). But Application of GA3 at lower level (100 p.p.m) gave highest values on GE as compared to G150, G200 and control treatments (fig 5). These results confirm the role of gibberellins in increasing the germination indices. These results were in line with the concept that when application of GA3 to the seeds can enhance the SVI, and DGS as reported by [21-22]. On contrast, increasing salt concentration resulting up to 100 milimoses in decreased of FGP, DGS and SVI (Figures 6,7 and 9) but increased MGT and GE as compared to control treatments (Figures 8 and 10). These results could be due to negative effects of salinity because salinity prevents water intake particularly with high salinity levels, and this causes enzymes inhibition and consequence leads to restriction of germination and seedling growth and increased germination time. Also, our results were in line with results found by previous workers [6] who stated that, increasing levels of salinity reduced in seed germination and affected growth of seedling in wheat. As mentioned earlier, the interaction effect was significant only on DGS. In this regard, application of Ga3 at 150 p.p.m decreased the salinity negative effects (Table 2). Although GAxS had none significant effects on PGP, GE, MGT and SVI but application of high levels of GA3 decreased the harmful of salinity on seed germination and affected growth of seedling (Table 2). This result might be confirmed with those reported by [16,23] who showed that, application of GA under salinity stress due to 100 mM NaCl alleviated the inhibitory effect of salinity leading to an increase in the rate of germination wheat seed. In conclusion, it was concluded that applied of GA3 at recommended levels lessened the harmful of salinity on germination indices and growth of seedling in wheat seeds.

REFERENCES

[1]. Wall, G.W.; Garcia, R.L.; Kimball, B.A.; Hunsaker, D.J.; Printer, P.J.; Long, P.; Osborne, C.P.; Hendrix, D.L.; Wechsung, F.; Wechsung, G.; Leavitt, S.W.; LaMorte, R.L. and Idso, B. (2006). Interactive Effects of Elevated Carbon Dioxide and Drought on Wheat. *Agron. J.*, 98:354-38

- [2]. Acevedo, E., Nachit, M. & Ortiz-Ferrara, G. (1998). Effects of heat stress on wheat and possible selection tools for use in breeding for tolerance. In: Wheat for nontraditional warm areas. Pp.401-421. D.A. Saunders (ed.). DF, CIMMYT, Mexico.
- [3]. **World Bank Agriculture and Food**. Available online: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/agriculture/overview> (accessed on 24 September 2024).
- [4]. Karanisa, T.; Amato, A.; Richer, R.; Abdul Majid, S.; Skelhorn, C. and Sayadi, S. (2021). Agricultural Production in Qatar's Hot Arid Climate. *Sustainability*, 13, 1-25.
- [5]. **Turkyilmaz B.**, 2012 - Effects of salicylic and gibberellic acids on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under salinity stress. *Bangladesh J. Bot.*, 41(1):29-34
- [6]. Hussain, S.; Khaliq, A.; Matloob, A.; Wahid, M. and Afzal, I. (2013). Germination and growth response of three wheat cultivars to NaCl salinity. *Soil Environ. 32(1): 36-43*
- [7]. Matter, H.M.; Ahmed, B.A. and Idris, A.O. (2024); Germination Indices and Seedling Growth Parameters in Maize under Salinity Stress with Varying Concentrations of Gibberellic Acid (GA) *Asian J. Adv. Agric. Res.*, 24(6):82-88.
- [8]. Mattar, H.M.; Ahmed, B.A. and Omar, A.A. (2024). Germination Indices and Seedling Growth Parameters in Maize under Salinity Stress with Varying Concentrations of Gibberellic Acid (GA). *Asian Journal of Advances in Agricultural Research*; 24(6):82-88.
- [9]. Çavuşoğlu, K., Kılıç, S., Kabar, K. (2007): Some morphological and anatomical observations in alleviating salt stress with gibberellic acid, kinetin and ethylene during germination of barley seeds. – *Sdü Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi (E-Journal)* 2(1): 27-40 (in Turkish).
- [10]. Saboora, A. and K. Kiarostami. 2006. Salinity tolerance of wheat genotype at germination and early seedling growth. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 9: 2009-2021.
- [11]. Mehmet, A., M.D. Kaya and G. Kaya. 2006. Effects of NaCl on the germination, seedling growth and water uptake of triticale. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry* 30: 39-47.
- [12]. Musyimi D.M., G.W. Netondo and G. Ouma. 2007. Effects of salinity on growth and photosynthesis of avocado seedling. *International Journal of Botany* 3: 78-84.
- [13]. Zhang H, Irving LJ, McGill C, Matthew C, Zhou D and Kemp P 2010. The effects of salinity and osmotic stress on barley germination rate: sodium as an osmotic regulator. *Ann. Bot.* **106**: 1027-1035
- [14]. Abari AK, Nasr MH, Hojjati M and Bayat D 2011. Salt effects on seed germination and seedling emergence of two *Acacia* species. *African J. Plant Sci.* **5**: 52-56.
- [15]. Kaveh H, Nemati H, Farsi M and Jartoodeh SV 2011. How salinity affect germination and emergence of tomato lines. *J. Biol. Environ. Sci.* **5**: 159-163.

- [16]. Samad, R . and Karmoker,JI.(2012). Effects of Gibberellic Acid and Kn on Seed Germination and Accumulation of Na⁺ And K⁺ In the Seedlings of Triticale-I under Salinity Stress. Bangladesh J. Bot. **41**(2): 123-129,
- [17]. Attia,H.; Alamer,KH.;Algethami,B.; Zorrig,W.;Hessini,W.; Gupta,K and Gupta,Bh.(2022). Gibberellic acid interacts with salt stress on germination, growth and polyamine gene expression in fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*. Mill.) seedlings. *Physiol Mol Biol Plants* (March 2022) **28**(3):607–622.
- [18]. Basra, S.M.A., M.N. Iftikhar and I. Afzal. 2011. Potential of moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) leaf extract as priming agent for hybrid maize seeds. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology* **13**: 1006–1010.
- [19]. Bewley, J.D. and M. Black. 1985. *Seeds: Physiology of Development and Germination*. Plenum Press, New York. 445p.
- [20]. Farooq, M., S.M.A. Basra, M. Khalid, R. Tabassum and T. Mehmood. 2006. Nutrient homeostasis, rearsvers metabolism and seedling vigor as affected by seed priming in coarse rice. *Canadian Journal of Botany* **84**: 1196–1202.
- [21]. Damalas, C. A., Koutroubas, S. D., and Fotiadis, S. (2019). Hydro-priming effects on seed germination and field performance of faba bean in spring sowing. *Agriculture*, **9**(9), 201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture9090201>
- [22]. Mohammed,A.H and Baldwin,B.S. (2023). Effect of Seed Priming With Gibberellic Acid (GA3) on Seed Germination and Seedling Growth of Some Barley Varieties (*Hordeum Vulgare* L.)*Tikrit Journal for Agricultural Sciences* (2023) **23** (2): 190-200.
- [23]. Oral, E.; Altuner, F.; Tunçtürk, R. and Tunçtürk, M(2019). The impact of salt (NaCl) stress on germination characteristics of gibberellic acid pretreated wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf) seeds. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research* **17**(5):12057-12071.

Fig 1 Means FGP as affected by GA3

Fig 2 Means DGS as affected by GA3

Fig 3 Means MGT as affected by GA3

Fig 4 Means SVI as affected by GA3

Fig 5 Means GE as affected by GA3

Fig 6 Means of F GP as affected by Salinity Stress

Fig 7 Means of D GS as affected by Salinity Stress

Fig 8 Means of M GT as affected by Salinity Stress

Fig 9 Means of SVI as affected by Salinity Stress

Fig 10 Means of GE as affected by Salinity Stress

Table 1 Means of Salinity x GA3 Interaction on Germination Indices and SVI of Wheat

Treatment		DGS	GE	SVI	FGP	MGT
S0	G0	2.32CD	93.37	97.16	93.37	0.01
	G100	3.57B	5.47	2.74	75.36	15.88
	G150	4.76A	45.63	53.24	99.90	99.87
	G200	3.57B	50.44	99.96	95.46	98.22
S50	G0	1.68DE	81.40	5.58	99.50	10.31
	G100	1.60DE	59.29	38.70	81.88	29.74
	G150	2.86BC	41.46	29.78	37.27	79.97
	G200	2.63BC	27.29	63.72	12.29	87.79
S100	G0	1.58DE	43.21	21.19	76.72	85.97
	G100	1.60DE	12.29	23.70	27.29	77.52
	G150	1.34E	4.98	12.30	4.98	65.20
	G200	1.51E	76.66	15.99	90.53	99.39
LSD0.05		0.08	6.79	7.44	4.11	4.63